

BESTIES Case Study Workstream Report

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Workstream Leaders

Name	Organisation
Katie Wilde	University of Aberdeen
Michael Smith	Manchester University NHS Foundation Trust
Michael Mallaburn	Manchester University NHS Foundation Trust
Simon Doran	Institute of Cancer Research, London
Joanna Wills	Collective Minds

Table 1: Case Study workstream leaders

1. Introduction

The BESTIES initiative set out to gather detailed, real-world case studies from imaging data environments across the UK and Europe. The aim was to understand how sites are actually handling pseudonymisation, anonymisation, data routing and governance — not in theory, but in practice. Four case studies were formally presented at the session. A fifth was volunteered on the day, and one was withdrawn prior to presentation due to information governance concerns.

2. Case Study Overview

Participating Sites

- Manchester University NHS FT (MFT) – BRAID Study (Breast Diagnostic Imaging)
- Aberdeen / iCAIRD / SHAIP – multisite retrospective work spanning mammography, MR and CT
- ICR & Royal Marsden (RM) – a well-established, XNAT-based pseudonymisation infrastructure dating back to 2013

- Collective Minds Radiology (EU consortium) – a large-scale collaborative platform operating across nine countries

2.1 Domains of Imaging

2.1.1 Case Study Domains

Between them, the case studies covered a reasonably broad range of imaging types and anatomical areas, including mammography, MRI, ultrasound and CT, as well as breast, colorectal and liver imaging. Musculoskeletal work was also represented, with wrist and ankle fractures included.

2.1.2 Audience-Suggested Missing Domains

A Slido poll asking “Are we missing any domains?” generated a lively response. PET came up most frequently, and there was a clear thread around neuroimaging — EEG and MEG both featured. Beyond that, participants flagged ophthalmology (retinal imaging), dental, digital pathology slides, DICOM and non-DICOM microscopy, functional MR, freehand SPECT, and patient-generated photographs or videos from clinic settings. There was also appetite for data fusion case studies covering multimodal integration. Taken together, these suggestions point to a substantially broader scope for BESTIES than the current case studies reflect, and they should feed directly into future submission priorities.

2.2. Access Environments and Technical Data Pipelines

2.2.1 Manchester – BRAID Study

Manchester pulled data via DIMSE C-MOVE from a Sectra PACS, with images received and processed through an Orthanc DICOM server. Pseudonymisation was handled using a Cambridge-provided Python script built on dicom-anonymizer, which was customised to cover DOB formatting, retention of device information, a bespoke accession-to-exam-ID mapping, and BurnedInAnnotation tagging.

Transfer to Cambridge XNAT ran into problems — approximately a third of images were going missing due to script limitations, which ultimately meant falling back to SFTP to complete the cohort delivery.

2.2.2 Aberdeen – iCAIRD / SHAIIP

Aberdeen’s pipeline draws from PACS using scheduled workflows built in collaboration with Philips. Pseudonymisation is handled through Hidden in Plain Sight (HIPS), applying an extensive ruleset of DICOM tag transformations. For mammography specifically, a number of additional tags are retained — Study Description, Contrast/Bolus Agent and Protocol Name — as these are needed downstream.

Processed data is made available through TRE workspaces that support researcher Docker containers alongside radiology reports, EMR data and letters, all under strict internal-only access controls. Aberdeen has also validated a federated learning workflow running across Aberdeen and Glasgow, with joint disclosure checks in place.

2.2.3 ICR & Royal Marsden

The ICR/RM setup uses a dual-XNAT architecture: one identifiable XNAT sits inside the RM network, while a second anonymised instance sits within the RM TRE or at ICR. The pipeline is highly automated — cohorts are defined via CSV, images are retrieved directly from the VNA, anonymisation is tailored per project, and SOPClassUID filtering is used to block secondary captures that might contain burned-in text.

The infrastructure has been running since 2013 and now supports over 300 XNAT projects, including roughly 20 multicentre trials.

2.2.4 Collective Minds

Collective Minds operates a zero-footprint cloud platform that supports both edge client upload and batch dataset ingestion. Work is organised into packages covering collaborative annotation, segmentation, model training and API access, and centralised validation. The scale is notable — by 2025, the platform had processed data from over 20,500 subjects

across more than 24,500 DICOM studies, generating in excess of 15,100 annotations, all across nine European countries.

2.3. Anonymisation & Pseudonymisation Processes

2.3.1. Manchester

Python with dicom-anonymizer, customised with bespoke DICOM tag substitutions. BurnedInAnnotation filtering was added specifically to catch burned-in patient identifiers.

2.3.2. Aberdeen

Hidden in Plain Sight applies detailed transformation rules across DICOM tags (categorised as C/D/K/U/X/Z operations). Retention of additional mammography-specific tags was identified as important for ensuring the data remains usable for downstream analysis.

2.3.3. ICR & RM

DicomEdit6-driven script selection, dynamically applied per study. The team has also been actively involved in research into pixel-level burned-in identifier detection through the MIDI-B benchmark work.

2.3.4 Collective Minds

NEMA-standard pseudonymisation via CM Connect, with automated pseudonym assignment and built-in quality checks throughout the pipeline.

2.4. Challenges

2.4.1. Manchester

The team faced a difficult set of circumstances from the outset. Engagement came late — after study closure — leaving very little time to work with. There was no dedicated funding for imaging informatics. Cohort metadata quality was a real problem: around 3.6% of the cohort had errors including wrong or swapped accession numbers, incorrect modalities, and unrelated scans (scapula images, for instance, appearing in what should have been a breast

imaging dataset). On top of this, the XNAT transfer script proved unreliable, resulting in an incomplete cohort.

2.4.2. Aberdeen

Integrating pseudonymisation directly within the TRE improves reproducibility and makes the overall workflow more robust. Scanner inconsistency was a recurring issue, and the team found it has a more direct impact on AI model performance than is often acknowledged.

2.4.3. ICR & RM

SSL and firewall issues caused intermittent instability with the XNAT Desktop Client. Getting software installed within NHS environments remains a governance headache. Burned-in text detection is still not fully solved, and this continues to be an area of active work.

2.4.4 Collective Minds

An early non-standard transfer route (sFTP) introduced PHI into the dataset, and remediating that took over 18 months. High scanner heterogeneity across nine countries also required significant harmonisation effort before the data could be used effectively.

2.5. Lessons Learned

2.5.1. Manchester

The experience underlined how important early engagement with imaging informatics teams is — being brought in after study closure left very little room to manoeuvre. Cohort metadata quality needs to be treated as a first-class concern, not an afterthought. Any scripted transfer process should have robust error checking and retry logic built in from the start.

2.5.2. Aberdeen

Integrating pseudonymisation directly within the TRE improves reproducibility and makes the overall workflow more robust. Scanner inconsistency was a recurring issue, and the team found it has a more direct impact on AI model performance than is often acknowledged.

2.5.3. ICR & RM

With the XNAT Desktop Client being deprecated, browser-based tooling is becoming essential rather than optional. Having a dedicated anonymisation server has proven its worth for long-term sustainability at scale.

2.5.4 Collective Minds

Harmonisation is non-negotiable in multi-country datasets. Broad intake protocols — designed to be permissive and handle variation gracefully — significantly reduce errors and make the overall pipeline more scalable.

2.6. Successes

2.6.1. Manchester

Despite the time pressure, the team secured the PACS access they needed and, in the process, built institutional knowledge that should make future studies significantly smoother.

2.6.2. Aberdeen

Aberdeen demonstrated large-scale AI testing in a real NHS setting — notably a COVID chest X-ray tool validated on 293,143 images, achieving radiologist-level accuracy. The federated learning demonstrator across two NHS regions was a significant milestone, and public and staff engagement work from the programme has been published.

2.6.3. ICR & RM

Having maintained a functioning anonymisation service across 300+ projects over 15 years is a substantial achievement. The team has also contributed actively to improving the DicomEdit anonymisation language in collaboration with XNAT developers.

2.6.4 Collective Minds

The platform has delivered a large, FAIR-aligned repository (20,000+ subjects) with reusable, well-curated cohorts — including 13,000+ in the breast cohort — and has established working pan-European collaboration infrastructure.

3. Workshop Feedback

In response to “What should we do next that would help you?” participants put forward several suggestions for what they needed:

A taxonomy of methods. - There was a request for a cross-case classification of architectures and pseudonymisation approaches. People want to be able to look across the case studies and understand what the options are in a structured way.

Joining up the Case Studies and Governance workstreams. - Several participants noted that the two workstreams are currently operating somewhat independently, and there is appetite to identify the gaps in the case study evidence base that would help inform the Governance workstream’s recommendations.

More case studies. - The current sample is valuable but not yet large enough to draw out general frameworks. A broader set of case studies would allow more robust abstractions to be made.

A poster or short publication. - There is real community interest in a jointly-authored, citable output that brings together findings from across the programme.

Demonstrating precedent and benefit. - Participants wanted clearer articulation of how the case studies establish precedent for particular approaches, and what the demonstrable benefits are — partly to support the case for adoption elsewhere.

Clarifying what ‘best practice’ looks like. - The audience wants to come away from BESTIES with a distilled, usable best-practice model, not just a collection of individual examples.

4. Next Steps

Immediate (0–3 months)

- Publish updated consolidated case studies.
- Produce a poster or short paper summarising findings across the programme.
- Begin developing a taxonomy of methods, covering pseudonymisation strategies, imaging data routing architectures, TRE integration models and multicentre ingestion patterns.

Medium-term (3–12 months)

- Use the consolidated case study insights to develop a BESTIES Best Practice Framework.

Long-term (>12 months)

- Expand case studies into new domains identified above
- Establish shared UK imaging pseudonymisation standards.